

Coping Strategy, Social Support of Mother with Stress in Cancer Patients in Dok II Jayapura Hospital (Qualitative Study)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Stress is a condition of tension that affects one's emotions, thought processes and conditions. Cancer sufferers experience emotional and psychological problems after knowing that they have cancer so that patients will experience stress. But according to research conducted by Cancer Research UK, UK concluded that cancer cases in women increased six times faster than men. From the results of observations and experiences and seeing the phenomenon that occurs at this time that the high level of stress experienced by housewives before getting sick, and when sick becomes an attraction for researchers to find out more. **Objective:** To find out mothers' feelings, care of medical staff about maternal feelings, forms of support received by mothers, benefits, strategies and barriers of mothers to cancer at RSUD Dok II Jayapura. **Writing Method:** qualitative research with Snowball Sampling techniques. In the data analysis, the researcher used Colaizzi analysis technique, the population in this study was the mother population with cancer at the Dok 2 Jayapura Hospital and her family as well as the medical staff in the room where the informant was. The study was carried out at RSUD Dok 2 Jayapura in April-May 2018. **Results:** In this study the feelings of the mother were sick (painful) and hopeless. As a medical person, we need to know the general condition of our care that is psycho, social and spiritual. Support is needed by mothers who have terminal disease (cancer), anyone involved must support including medical personnel in providing information support, so that mothers feel cared for and even have quality of life despite obstacles in the healing process. One that can make a mother survives and even

recovers by starting a healthy lifestyle NEW START.

Keywords: Stress, Coping, Cancer, Dok II Jayapura Hospital.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is a condition of tension that affects emotions, the process of thinking and one's condition. Cancer sufferers experience emotional and psychological problems after knowing that they have cancer so that patients will experience stress. Stress in cancer patients can be caused by a variety of reasons including psychological reactions caused by cancer diagnosis, treatment side effects, age, education, socioeconomic. Besides that, the stage of cancer and social support. Fear of death, cannot continue with its life plans, (Yusuf Maulana Nur, 2015). It is known that in 2012 there were 14,067,894 new cases of cancer and 8,201,575 cancer deaths worldwide. In Indonesia, the prevalence of cancer in women is 1.4 per 1,000 population (Risksdas 2013), this cancer is the biggest problem for women in Papua, each year an estimated 546 Papuan women die of cervical cancer, the most findings were found in RSUD Dok II Jayapura is a referral hospital from various districts in Papua (Sandjaya, 2012). From the results of observations and experiences and seeing the phenomenon that occurs at this time that the high level of stress experienced by housewives before getting sick, and when sick becomes an attraction for researchers to find out more. Based on the description

above, the researcher is interested in conducting research on "Stress, Coping Strategies and Mother's Social Support with Cancer in RSUD Dok II Jayapura (Qualitative Study).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The type of research used is qualitative research with Snowball Sampling techniques. The population in this study was the maternal population with cancer at Dok 2 Jayapura Hospital and their families and medical personnel in the room where the informants were. The numbers of informants in this study were five informants. The research was carried out at Dok 2 Jayapura Hospital in April-May 2018. analysis of the data of the researcher used Colaizy analysis technique, Colaizy analysis.

RESEARCH RESULTS

1) Mother's feelings

1.1. Sensory Feelings

All mothers feel pain (pain), following the statement,

"It's too tight and scary, sick here (while the mother points to the breast with *Ca.mammae*) until at the waist, back and forth all the pain, (Informant 1, Friday, 4/14/2018).

"All bodies are sick, congested, feeling hot body too (Informant 2, Friday, 14/4/2018).

"It hurts, behind this kind of pain the bones want to break, so sleep continues (Informant 3, Friday, 14/4/2018).

"It's a pain to get to the bones until I get a hand, it hurts from August (Informant 4 Friday, 14 / 4/ 2018).).

"I have a heart pounding, my stomach is all sore, back and forth are also sick (Informant 5 Friday 04/14/2018).

1.2. Feelings of Vital Life:
In this study there were two statements from five informants. The first and second informants said about the feeling of vital life, the following statement:
"Oh no, I don't want to eat first, the doctor sucks first to eat, if the doctor does not feel sick and less crowded (Informant 1 Friday

04/14/2018).

"Call the nurse first and become more crowded (the mother talks stammered with O2 attached because of tightness, attached to a kettle, both arms and legs are swollen so that the mother cannot move, all are assisted by family and medical), already tired, have this suffering so long enough (Informant 2 Friday 04/14/2018).

1.3. Psychological feeling

In this study, one to five informants said their psychological feelings, the following statement,

"I don't think anything, the money problem also doesn't think that I think I have a cure (Informant 1, Friday 04/14/2018).

"I feel stressed and suffer from this disease, I think it's a place to stay away from the place of service, three times referral, I have this suffering, but it is not enough but I do not know whether it is not (Informant 2 Friday 04/14/2018).

"I think that children are illiterate (5 children) if the other children are okay but I have sixth graders who are taking this exam (While mother is crying) I can't take care of her if she goes for exams (Informant 3 Friday 14 / 4/2018).

"Feelings of sadness because the tongs hurt can come here, sad because they remember the children, a sense of burden for the family, this wants chemo but no blood goals B is postponed until there is blood from the new PMI transfusion can be chemo (Informant 4 Friday 04/14/2018).

"It's sad, my mind, I just sat crying, crying not disappointed but remember having a child, I want you to have a happy child with other mothers too (Mom, crying and wiping tears) but it's always good for God, it's ready if God wants to use it, so I have this life to serve God (Informant 5 Friday 04/14/2018).

1.4. Feeling of personality:

In this study, four of the five informants felt feelings of despair, lack of enthusiasm and a long feeling of healing, following the statement of the informant, namely, "It's been reconciled here twice (RSUD Dok II

Jayapura) but not cured (Informant 1 Friday 04/14/2018).

"In October 2014 I had surgery in Merauke, was stressed and suffering from this disease, I didn't know whether I was cured or not (Informant 2 Friday 04/14/2018). "It's been sick from August 2017 (Mother's hair looks bald) It's been five times chemo but no changes (Informant 4 Friday 04/14/2018). "This disease is what I fear is dialysis, Oh I don't want to, but the thought is now that I want to have it out of my way to have children at home (Informant 5 Friday 04/14/2018)

2) Concern for Health Workers

Based on the results of research on feelings of information, researchers found the informants' feelings, namely feeling of pain, shortness, heat, despair, resignation and even an informant who refused the planned medical action. The following is the statement of the medical staff (Nurse) about the feelings of the mother while being treated at the RSUD Dok II Jayapura. "About the feelings of mothers with cancer in the room, of course we also know how he feels, let alone the average patient with an end-stage, despair is certain, wondering how to get well or not? Well, we, as medical personnel, can only give encouragement, motivation for mothers. in our room there is indeed a rule from the head of the room directly to reprimand greetings, if the mother looks moody, or asks while being angry unclear, we approach us to ask carefully, is there a problem with the mother getting angry? or every operand in our patient's room greet, selamat, morning / afternoon / evening mom how do you feel today? we do it even though there are often officers who are negligent (Nurse room 17/4/2018). "We used to encourage mothers to be strong, especially if they are going to chemo. here there is no special treatment for our cancer patients (Nurses and midwives) who are used to encouraging the mother (Nurse room 4/17/2018)."

3) Family supports mother

In this study, families provided Emotional support, rewards, information and instruments at the hospital and at home, statements from informants "I'm happy when my family comes to me, if I tell you so I don't focus too much on the sick (pointing at the breast of the informant (Informant 1, Friday 04/14/2018). "The husband said that he must be cured, we want to go back to our children's village (Informant 2, Monday 04/17/2018)"Father (husband) said that I think things like that, we justify everything to God (Informant 3, Monday 04/17/2018) "Husband says don't tackle the mind with disease (Informant 4 Monday 17/4/2018). "Mama and you said we prayed and tried to heal God alone (Informant 5 Monday 4/17/2018). In the research results, the five informants felt the support from the family so that the mother felt not alone. In this category there are five statements from five informants about the award support given to mothers during illness, the following statement: "All have children who have been sick for a while until late, usually when they are sick they rub in a backward fashion (Informant 1, Monday 17/4/2018). "There is a husband, but he goes to and fro if the nurse calls, luckily there is a sister (While pointing to the sister of the participant who is standing next to the participant) she who takes care of me has all of the sick still at home again until down at the hospital this time he took care of it (Informant 2, Monday 04/17/2018).

"This father who served me, was sick when I was at home the father who cared for the children and also the children, all the working men (Informant 3, Monday 4/17/2018).

"Husband, parents are also the usual guard here (RS), usually take blood at PMI, this husband again checks blood in (Informant 4, Monday, 04/17/2018). "The older brother from there is a referral until here in Jayapura because the husband works so he can't join (Informant 5, Monday, 04/17/2018). 1)

Support of Health Workers In this study mothers with cancer only received informational support from health workers as follows, "I am patient, yach the doctor has just come later, I ask if you are on a biopsy / function today or not? (Nurse - informant 1, Monday 17/4/2018).

"I just wait for the schedule for chemotherapy; the mother is not chemo because you have to eat a lot first, because the mother is lacking red blood cells (hemoglobin) / anemia. yes, mother just prayed that God will give mother strength, mother must be strong (Informant Nurse 2, Monday 04/17/2018)

"I am getting ready because there are plans for chemotherapy before my mother returns home, she prays that everything is smooth, she can go home (nurse to informant 3)

"Mom, maybe the chemo was the last on the 3rd, but if there was already blood B at PMI, the mother could have transfused then chemotherapy, mother ate, rested regularly, not many thoughts, ma'am (doctor - Informant 4, Monday 04/17/2018).

"I talked with my mother's family first because my mother planned to have dialysis (Doctor of Informants 5, Monday, 04/17/2018).

4) Benefits of Support for mothers

In this study, four out of five informants benefited from social support, but there were also informants who did not feel the benefits of social support at home so that they did not want to depend on God, the following statement. "Usually assisted by family, neighbors are also manokwari, neighbors come see, stories, yes I feel happy, when I sit down the story is not too thoughtful with this pain to give strength, tell me so that I am not too sick with this illness. Here at the hospital there is an om from arso coming to see, also from the church come praying, happy to be strong. (Informant 1, Tuesday, 04/18/2018). "In the house so that I will be sick for a long time

but there are no neighbors who come to see me, but it's not too much of a mind because there is a family who is my friend (Informant 04, Friday 04/14/2018). "I used to say that I prayed a lot, but I said you were praying, but what kind of God did you hear, you prayed, I was lazy to pray, but you said, don't say that, God never gave up living, think too, so Sa just love this life for God (Informant 4, Friday 04/14/2018).

5) Coping Strategy

In this category two of the five informants said that the coping strategies taken during illness were the following statement "I don't think anything else, I think I want to recover, that's all (Informant 1, Tuesday, 04/18/2018). "Dong want to make what, what, (medical action) I come because I want to get well (Informant 3, Tuesday, 04/18/2018). 2) Obstacles from Social Support In this category two of the five informants who said there were barriers to social support during illness, along with statements from two informants and four informants, namely: "In October 2017 I was operating at Merauke Hospital and after the completion of the operation I was planned to be referred to Jayapura Hospital for chemo but the Sister in Merauke said I could not get a mother because this year I want to close the book so there is no money, I am stressed and almost want to hit he, finally I returned to the village of Amenda, Haju District, Mappi Regency, until I returned to the village, I finally returned (Informant 2, Friday 04/14/2018). "In the house so that I will be sick for a long time but there are no neighbors who come to see me, but it's not too much of a mind because there is a family who is my friend (Informant 04, Monday 04/17/2018).

by the health department and the physical administration department of Lantamal X by determining the time and day of exercise that must be carried out for the purpose of improving / maintaining the physical condition of the body and controlling the condition, physical abilities

of each personnel. The work program of the physical field administration service Lantamal X conducted the tests per semester (per 6 months) with the aim of monitoring the health condition of X's personnel, which was carried out, namely running in 12 minutes, restock, sit ups, pussy up. The health office has routine personnel (Urikes) health screening programs per semester (per 3 months) to monitor and monitor the health of personnel where the work program can

determine the health conditions of personnel physically and spiritually.

Lantamal X has sports facilities for personnel and families fitness equipment, restock, badminton court, futsal court, foot soccer field, archery field, volleyball court and residence / residential safe personnel, fresh air, away from public highways where it is wrong one cause of environmental population.

DISCUSSION

1. Mother's feelings

With a feeling of happiness, said the patient can reduce his focus on illness (Maria, 2010). The mother's way of coping with her feelings must be based on her own understanding, speaking to herself positively replacing negative thoughts like mother's feelings whether I will recover? as in medicine there is no change, so the mother rejects medical action. Mother's feelings should imagine that she is coping with the problem

2. Concern for medical personnel

As a medical person, we need to know the general condition of our care that is psycho, social and spiritual. A well-known stress management practitioner named Donald Tubesing, said that there are six main things that cause stress in everyday cancer sufferers, namely, act rashly, health workers, try to control everything, maintain bad health habits, keep pessimistic feelings prolonged, always hold on to the past and believe in conflicting values (Tubesing Donald, 2000 in his Health household). According to Doctor Maria, severely ill patients who carry out palliative care can usually survive longer than doctors' verdicts. Mothers with cancer who experience suffering need an integrated approach to various disciplines so that the patient has a good quality of life and dies in dignity at the end.

3. Family support

Support is very necessary and very much needed by mothers who have terminal disease (cancer), especially the support of the family. not only family but anyone must support. Support from parents, family, government through health workers, Indonesian cancer foundation (YKI), cancer foundation in Jayapura city.

4. Medical Staff Support

Medical personnel must inform the mother honestly about the treatment process. Health workers and families must explain, the situation of the treatment process that the mother is undergoing, give advice, advice, instructions and input to the mother so that the mother understands the situation and the mother knows the instructions that the mother must make during treatment so that the mother feels respected and valued by the family and health workers. The thing that must be done by health workers / hospitals is to work together between doctors, nurses and psychologists in providing support to mothers with cancer through palliative care that focuses on reducing the symptoms of disease intensity. Therefore, it can be concluded that the goals of psycho-oncology and palliative care run parallel to one another.

5. Benefits of Support

One of the benefits of support for cancer patients is to share their experiences and secrets with fellow cancer patients. Liong Pit Lin, who is a cancer patient, opened a kind of private consultation that was free of charge. Within a week, there were 35-80 patients who came to him. It is very useful that is always positive thinking in order to control ourselves, thoughts and patterns of life and sports. If we can take care of our lives in the first 40 years we live, then health will take care of us in the next 40 years. "The importance of a healthy lifestyle help us to be able to feel the world longer. the mother accepts the presence of cancer as His provision. Ikhlas, whatever nature brings to us, we do not fight. This is determined there must be a message that God wants to convey. We follow His scenario, "he added." Cancer patients are expected to be able to bring more positive awareness in themselves so that they can escape the two negative consciousnesses that are often experienced by cancer patients namely helplessness and hopelessness (Rahmi Fitria, 2018).

6. Coping is good for mothers with cancer

The best coping in mothers with cancer is religious coping. In general, someone who has faith in God when faced with a stressful situation, then the individual will involve God and other religious elements in overcoming the problem (back to religion). This means that coping (problem solving) conducted using the divine approach, According to Wong-McDonald and Gorsuch, religious coping is a way for individuals to use their beliefs in managing stress and problems in life (Maryam siti, 2017).

7. Obstacles

The first thing we do is when we find ourselves sick and get stuck with, what we have to do by looking for info. If we find obstacles in the healing process of cancer we should learn from the story of the

healing of others, especially directly from the person, that is the best way. Thursday, February 24, 2011 I, (Andre Laksono) and his wife attended the seminar on Ms. Liong Pit Lin entitled Cancer, Is There Still Hope. Fellow cancer sufferers need to know for themselves (without being represented because health problems and healing cannot be represented) how to cure patients with cancer (Laksono Andre, 2011).

Can cancer be cured? This question was answered firmly by Ms. Pit Lin: CAN (yes, Mrs. Liong Pit Lin himself a real example) how to, Avoid cancer triggers / carcinogens namely, chemical pollution both in food ingredients such as preservatives, coloring, fried foods, burned; as well as on what we wear like lotion bodies, polishes, perfumes, insect repellent, car perfumes, air fresheners, Avoid living in an environment of factory pollution, waste, roadside with heavy traffic. Avoid eating meat, chicken, fish eggs that are bred with pellets / injections of fattening hormones (Laksoso Andre, 2011). For healing, do 8 elements abbreviated by Pit Lin as NEW START.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of a study at the Dok II Jayapura Hospital in May-April 2018, the five informants found that mothers felt a feeling of pain, tightness, so they did not want to eat and feelings of uncertainty to recover, so that even though the mother was accompanied by a family during illness, the mother was still worried about his health condition. One of the best forms of support for mothers with cancer is palliative care and the implementation of a healthy NEW START lifestyle on the physical, psychological, social and spiritual aspects. Palliative care place is a hospital, for patients who have to get treatment that requires close supervision, special measures or special equipment, while the NEW START lifestyle can be a home, hospital or anywhere.

SUGGESTIONS

a) Hospital

It is recommended to the Jayapura Public Hospital II to work together between medical staff, psychologists and diversity in preparing special care services for patients with cancer, namely palliative care.

It was suggested to the General Hospital of Dok II Jayapura to create a health seminar program for cancer patients and invite speakers who had recovered from cancer such as Pit Lin's mother to share the experience of recovering from cancer to be a motivation for other cancer patients to follow the healing process that Mother Pit Lin do.

Planning a NEW START healthy life program for cancer patients who were treated at Dok II Jayapura Hospital, with no medical treatment (RS only controls the progress of the disease) so that patients feel a change and continue the NEW START lifestyle when returning home.

b) Health Workers

It is recommended to health workers, so that they need to have insight and knowledge about the importance of palliative care and healthy lifestyle NEW START for patients with cancer, so that health workers can educate on how to recover from cancer to mothers and families so that mothers can have hope to recover and live longer with loved ones.

c) Society

Disaran to the public to be able to dig up information from books and the internet about cancer treatment experiences from cancer patients before, so that it can be an example to be applied in the healing process.

d) For Researchers

From the results of this study, researchers

would like to suggest and convince informants about how to recover from cancer with a healthy lifestyle NEW START. Let the informant surrender life to the creator because everything that happens above this world must have a purpose from the creator. Let the life giver give strength to the informant who while struggling with the illness. Humans may try, may plan but God determines.

e) For Further Researchers

It is hoped that we can develop further research related to this research, that is, can stress cause cancer in? and Can the lifestyle of NEW START patients with cancer be cured?

REFERENCES

- Agus, (2013). *Ini resep Liong Pit Lin berhasil sembuh dari kanker kronis*.<https://health.detik.com/berita-detikhealth/d-2300250/ini-resep-liong-pit-lin-berhasil-sembuh-dari-kanker-kronis>
-Fabella T Armand, (1998). *Buku anda sanggup mengatasi stress*. Hal 10-50
- Endriko dan Suwanto, (2016). *Gejala psikologis umum perasaan*. <http://www.Semuapsikologikita.com/2016/10/psikologis-umum-perasaan.html> 6/13/2017
- Friedman (2010). *Jenis-jenis dukungan keluarga*.<http://erepo.unud.ac.id/10071/3/241c310e95640d599699492e4612d50b.pdf>
- Globacan, (2012). *Statistik kanker*. <http://lawan.kanker.org/statistik-kanker>
- Laksono Andre, (2011). *Sembuh dari kanker Liong Pit Lin*. <https://id-id.facebook.com/notes/iyb-ilmu-yang-bermanfaat/inspirasi-sembuh-dari-kanker-cara-liong-pit-lin-a3/226402514061902/>
- Maria (2010). *Pasien kanker parah perlu perawatan paliatif biar senang*. <https://health.detik.com/berita-detikhealth/d-1337537/pasienkanker-parah-perlu-perawatan-paliatif-biar-senang>
- Masa,(2014). *Perasaanemosi*.http://www.academia.edu/7261857/Psikologi_individu
- Maulandari Novi, (2010). *Strategi koping menghadapi stres pada penderita kanker paru*.

- File:///C:/Users/ASUS/Downloads/Documents/f100040159.pdf
- Ninggali Retno, (2013). *Stres, gangguan psikologis dan hubungannya dengan kondisi fisik*. <http://majalah1000guruNet/2013/06/stress-gangguan-psikologis-fisik/>.
 - Nurbaiti Lia,(2014), *Kepribadian sehat*. <https://wordpress.com/2014/04/26>
 - Putri Saktian Anisa, (2018). *Mengenal Lebih Dalam Perawatan Paliatif untuk Pasien Kanker*. <https://www.vemale.com/kesehatan/119138-mengenal-lebih-dalam-perawatan-paliatif-untuk-pasien-kanker.htm>
 - Putu, (2016). *Kasus kematian kanker diJayapura semakin tinggi*. <https://www.cnnindonesia.com/nasional/Sabtu27/02/2016/01:36wit/kasus-kematian-akibat-kanker-di-jayapura-semakin-tinggi/>
 - Riswato, (2011). *Definisi Perasaan Dan Emosi*. <https://riswatobk.com/2011/05/02/definisi-perasaan-dan-emosi/>
 - Rosaline, (2017). *Dr. Rosaline Irene Rumaseuw: penderita kanker serviks dipapua tertinggi di Indonesia*. Com/news/2017/11/08.
 - Sanjaya, (2012). *Kanker serviks dan kanker payudarterbanyak di Papua*. <http://radiosuaradogyaifm.co.id/2012/07/kanker-serviks-dan-payudara-terbanyak.html>
 - Saraswati Widya, (2014). *Stres dengan kanker, kaitan antara*. [http://npid-pass.com/article-kesehatan/kaitan-stres-dengan kanker/](http://npid-pass.com/article-kesehatan/kaitan-stres-dengan-kanker/)
 - Sari, (2010). *Hubungan Dukungan Suami Dengan Lama Persalinan Kala II Di RB AN NISSA Surakarta*. eprints.ac.id/pdf
 -Sehat Menteri, (2016). *Sehat menteri*. <https://sdabali.org/bali-sehat-ministry/>
 - Trefina Evi, (2017). *Cerita perjuangan Evi penyintas kanker serviks*. <https://www.cnnindonesia.com/gayahidup/20170418005159-255-208233/cerita-perjuangan-evie-trefina-penyintas-kanker-serviks>
 - Tubesing Donal, (2000). *Rumah Tangga dan kesehatan* Hal. 67

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